

A Study on Consumer Perception and Adoption of Electric Vehicle: A Behavioural Study

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Abstract

The need for sustainable transport has intensified its focus on EVs, especially two-wheelers, owing to ever-increasing environmental concerns and oscillating fuel prices. This study considers consumer perception and adoption patterns regarding two-wheeler EVs while analysing the behavioural factors that affect purchasing decisions. The present study favours EVs due to economic friendliness, lower operating cost and government incentives. Whereas hurdles that can limit acceptance are in the form of high upfront costs, a lack of charging infrastructure, and range anxiety. The explorative study used a statistical analysis of ANOVA and chi-square tests to show significant relationships between consumer awareness channels and the future buying intentions. In conclusion, the study asserts that improving charging infrastructure, consumer awareness, and policies in support of EV adoption will go a long way in enhancing the future of sustainable transportation.

Keywords: *Electric vehicles, Consumer behaviour, Two wheelers, Perception, Willingness, Purchase.*

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Introduction

The automobile is affected by increased concern about environmental degradation as well as rising fuel prices and the pressure globally towards sustainable development, hence the advent of Electric Vehicles (EVs) as an alternative to fuel-powered vehicles. EVs continue to be more popular among consumers because they are green, cheap to operate, and equipped with advancing technology. However, the speed at which consumers buy EVs varies considerably from consumer to consumer considering the different perceptions, social behaviour, and market dynamics. Understanding consumer perception and behavioural factors becomes imperative to assessing adoption patterns concerning EVs. Environmental awareness, cost factors, trusting technological change,

government policies, and provision of charging infrastructure help influence consumer decisions. However, despite an increasing trend, there still exist other barriers impeding consumer acceptance such as range anxiety, high initial cost, and lack of awareness. The study purports to assess the perceptions, preferences, and behavioural attributes affecting consumers' decisions in adopting electric vehicles. The research focuses on identifying the critical aspects that promote effective policy formulation and potential avenues of intervention for specific barriers affecting the promotion of EV adoption. Ultimately, this will lend itself to a more sustainable future of transport.

Objectives:

1. To know the concept of electric vehicle.
2. To analyse the customers perception on two-wheeler electric vehicle.

Review of literature:

“Electric Vehicle Adoption: A Comprehensive Systematic Review of Technological, Environmental, Organizational and Policy Impacts” (2024), by “Rami Zaino, Vian Ahmed, Ahmed Mohamed Alhammadi, Mohamad Alghoush”, in “World Electric Vehicle Journal” – This study provides information about impact of electric vehicle on technology, environment, business, innovation and policy. It also gives knowledge on government initiatives.

“Life cycle assessment of electric vehicles: a systematic review of literature”, by “Pabitra Kumar Das, Mohammad Younus Bhat, Shambhu Sajith” (2023), in “Environmental Science and Pollution Research” – This study gives knowledge about life cycle assessment evaluation of electric vehicles by highlighting their nature friendly benefits or advantages, which includes decrease in emission up to 97% compare to petrol vehicles.

Research gap:

The more study need on rural infrastructure for EV chargers with their less availability of electricity. Less study on vehicles indirect cost like maintenance cost with resale value and Impact of government regulations and policies on EVs.

Methodology

This study provides knowledge from both primary and secondary data. Primary data is collected information from public using questionnaire by convenience sampling with a response of 70. In 70 respondent's majority were male candidates with a age group of 21-30 by following salaried respondents were more with education of under graduation.

Results

Electric vehicles are a vehicle which runs through electric power without petrol or diesel. Electric vehicles mainly include car, bike, bus and other vehicles. This are cost effectives with rechargeable batteries and more environmentally friendly.

Figure 1. SWOT Analysis of the Electric Vehicles

Strengths:

- **Nature friendly:** EVs doesn't harm nature or environment which doesn't generates any emission or carbon footprint.
- **Less expenses on operation:** In EVs there will no more expenses of fuel or maintenance cost compare to traditional vehicles.
- **Support from government:** Government is supporting nature friendly or sustainable vehicles which is EVs by providing tax incentives, subsidies and other incentives to increase adoption.

Weakness:

- **More initial investment:** Initially cost will be more when purchasing new EVs comparing petrol or diesel vehicles.
- **Less charging facilities:** There is fewer charging stations can lead inconvenience at emergency time.
- **High or long charging hours:** Charging an electric vehicle takes longer than refuelling a gas to vehicle.

Opportunities:

- **Increased demand:** Increasing awareness will improve the demand of electric vehicles in upcoming days.
- **Technological advancement:** Sustainable improvement or advancement in EV will helps in more innovation.

- **New market segments:** Emerging markets for electric two-wheelers, buses and trucks present new opportunities.

Threats:

- **Changes in regulation & policies:** Many alternatives in rules and regulations of government will also affects the customers perception.
- **Hesitated by consumer:** As the charging capacity is less it will also affect customer priority.
- **Alternative competitors:** CNG & other nature friendly vehicles play major role as competitors for EVs.

Collected data from 70 respondents, 64 respondents were aware of two-wheeler vehicles and 60 respondents were ridden the two-wheeler vehicles with majority of them are male respondents.

To Analyze the Customers Perception on Two-Wheeler Electric Vehicle

H₀: There is no significant difference in customer perception across demographic profile of occupation.

H₁: There is significant difference in customer perception across demographic profile of occupation.

Table 1. One-way

ANOVA					
Importance of 2-wheeler EV vehicle brands					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	4.834	2	2.417	3.655	.031
Within Groups	44.309	67	.661		
Total	49.143	69			

Source: SPSS Software

Table 2. Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons						
Dependent Variable: Importance of 2-wheeler EV vehicle brands						
Tukey HSD						
(I) Occupation of respondents	(J) Occupation of respondents	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Salaried	Business owner/ Self employed	-.49825*	.19861	.038	-.9743	-.0222
	Retired	.36842	.58997	.807	-1.0457	1.7825
Business owner/ Self employed	Salaried	.49825*	.19861	.038	.0222	.9743
	Retired	.86667	.59389	.317	-.5568	2.2902
Retired	Salaried	-.36842	.58997	.807	-1.7825	1.0457
	Business owner/ Self employed	-.86667	.59389	.317	-2.2902	.5568

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Source: SPSS Software

In this, One-way ANOVA test the result says that accept alternative hypothesis (H_1) of “There is significant difference in customer perception across various demographic profile” which is below significant value or P-Value of 0.05 that is 0.038.

The Post hoc test (Tukey HSD) result says that salaried and business owner/ self-employed group shows more significant compare to other groups which is 0.038.

H₀: There is no significant relationship by where consumer is getting knowledge about two-wheeler EV and their willingness to purchase in future.

H₁: There is significant relationship by where consumer is getting knowledge about two-wheeler EV and their willingness to purchase in future.

Table 3. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	42.923 ^a	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	32.979	6	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	28.764	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	70		

a. 8 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .23.

Source: SPSS Software

Above SPSS analysis provides the result of reject null hypothesis (H_0) and accept alternative hypothesis (H_1) of “There is significant relationship by where consumer is getting knowledge about two-wheeler EV and their willingness to purchase in future” which significant or P-Value is below 0.05 that is 0.000.

Conclusion

The rise in the adoption of two-wheeler electric vehicles (EVs) can be attributed to growing environmental concerns, government incentives, and their cost-effectiveness. This study reveals that consumer perceptions differ based on demographic factors, with salaried professionals and self-employed individuals displaying a higher interest in adopting EVs. Key motivators include lower operational costs and eco-friendliness, while obstacles such as high initial costs, insufficient charging infrastructure, and range anxiety impede broader acceptance. Statistical analysis indicates a significant link between consumer awareness and their willingness to purchase EVs. To enhance adoption, it is essential to expand charging networks, lower battery costs, and boost consumer awareness. Policymakers and manufacturers need to work together to improve infrastructure, offer better financing options, and advance battery technology. A strategic focus on affordability, accessibility, and education will help accelerate the transition to sustainable electric mobility in India.

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